

 foodclik.eu

DELIVERABLE 5.3

ONLINE WEBSITE / PLATFORM

ICLEI EUROPE

31-03-2023

Funded
by the European Union

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PROJECT NUMBER:	101060717
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WORK PACKAGE LEADER:	ICLEI ES
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Work Package 5 of the EU-funded project FoodCLIC focuses on communication, dissemination and exploitation actions. As part of **Task 5.2 “Communication and dissemination”** of that work package, the project website has been developed and is now accessible online.

The online platform constitutes a key communication tool and central dissemination channel of the project. Its main purpose is to promote FoodCLIC, to explain the project approach and to ensure the project’s online visibility.

Different communication and dissemination channels converge on the project website. Measures executed through other (online and offline) communication channels (e.g. project partners’ websites) will have the aim to guide external stakeholders to the FoodCLIC website, which is functioning as a central information platform for external as well as internal stakeholders, summarizing key project information and showcasing achievements and results of project partners’ collaboration.

The main target groups of the website are the general public, scientists, politicians and policy makers at different governance levels (local, national, regional, EU) and local authorities as well as food policy networks, higher educational institutions and the FoodCLIC project partners.

The FoodCLIC website is accessible at the URL www.foodcllic.eu.

1. WEBSITE STRUCTURE

To achieve the best possible user friendliness, i.e. to ensure that visitors can navigate through the website intuitively, the website is structured in a clear and easy-to-understand manner with information relevant for each communication target audience.

All pages and sub-pages can be accessed through the well visible **menu** (button) that is placed in the website header and stays visible, when scrolling down the page.

Figure 1: Screenshot of FoodCLIC website, header on homepage with menu button.

Figure 2: Screenshot of FoodCLIC website, website menu opened.

For now (March 2023), the menu provides access to the following pages: **ABOUT**, **BLOG**, **CITY-REGIONS** (i.e. 8 sub-pages representing each of the FoodCLIC city-regions), and **CONTACT**.

Further sections, such as the **KNOWLEDGE HUB**; a **NEWSLETTER** subscription page and a **PRESS** corner, which are not part of the initial website launch, will be added in the further course of the project. The menu structure can be adapted at any time and may grow or change as the project progresses.

2. WEBSITE CONTENT

The FoodCLIC online platform provides visitors with up-to-date information on the project and insights into the partners' project-related work (**HOME PAGE**, **BLOG** page, **ABOUT** page and **CITY-REGION** pages). As a whole, the website content shall provide responses to the question as to how more inclusive and sustainable urban food environments across different city-regions can be created.

In collaboration with work package 4, it will be examined, how the website and particularly the eight city-region pages can serve as a virtual space (platform) to host and support the Food Policy Networks and higher education institutions.

Additionally, major (public and open access) project results, publications, material and resources will be promoted on the website and made available for download (**KNOWLEDGE HUB**).

The **KNOWLEDGE HUB** will serve as a data-sharing platform and present FoodCLIC's key project outcomes, produced materials as well as developed tools of all work packages to support policy makers and practitioners operating at different levels of governance in decision-making and impact assessment, amongst others. In the further course of the project, WP5-beneficiaries will examine the possibility of interlinking or integrating the FoodCLIC KNOWLEDGE HUB with (already established) topic-related online platforms with similar purposes (e.g. other EU projects' knowledge hubs), to create synergies. Additionally, it will be examined, how the KNOWLEDGE HUB can support exploitation activities (Task 5.4).

At the same time, the website serves as point of contact, providing visitors with contact information (**CONTACT** page), such as the central FoodCLIC email address, and the possibility to subscribe for the project newsletter, which will be sent out regularly in the course of the project.

The project website is a place, where the **FoodCLIC visual identity** and the **tone of voice** are presented in a consistent way, as defined in the FoodCLIC Design Style Guide (internal document, shared with the project consortium) and the FoodCLIC Communication and Dissemination Plan (D5.2). The project logo, colours as well as the unique FoodCLIC icon are showcased in line with the specifications made in the FoodCLIC Design Style Guide. Additionally, the website gives visibility to the EU funding.

Figure 3: Screenshot of FoodCLIC website, website footer, including the project logo and the EU funding acknowledgement.

As stated in the Grant Agreement, to increase FoodCLIC's impact, 48+ blog articles and 100+ project outputs as well as 16+ short videos will be published on the FoodCLIC website, serving a broad audience.

2.1 HOMEPAGE

In many cases, the homepage serves as the entry point for visitors who access the FoodCLIC website. Its purpose is therefore to provide visitors with an easily understandable overview of the website structure and content.

The FoodCLIC homepage welcomes visitors with a dynamic and illustrative **slider** at the top of the page, including a well visible button to access the **website menu**. Several content sections linking to the main web pages follow suit:

- A short **introductory part** outlines the main idea of the project, linking to the **ABOUT** page with more detailed project information.
- A section to highlight the last published **BLOG entries** (news, events ...).
- An overview of all **city-regions** with links to each of the eight city-region sub-pages.
- A presentation of all project partner organisations. For each organisation, the respective logo with a link to their (external) website is included.
- The website footer.

Figure 4: Screenshot of FoodCLIC website, homepage (upper part).

Figure 5: Screenshot of FoodCLIC website, homepage (lower part).

2.2 ABOUT PAGE

The **ABOUT** page provides interested stakeholders with more detailed, **general project information**. It includes explanations on the project objective(s) and the approach followed by the project consortium to implement the project.

Specifically, the FoodCLIC ABOUT page introduces the (technical) terms “*urban food environment*”, “*Food Policy Network*” and the project’s foundational, theoretical framework, “*the CLIC*”, to provide visitors with an understanding of the project context.

To familiarise external stakeholders with the project structure, the ABOUT page contains a **graphic map**, marking the eight FoodCLIC city-regions with the project partners located in each of the areas, and presenting the supporting research and network partners.

PEOPLE. FOOD. POLICY. PLACES.

LET'S CREATE SUSTAINABLE URBAN FOOD ENVIRONMENTS.

TO PROVIDE HEALTHY, SUSTAINABLE, AFFORDABLE + ATTRACTIVE FOOD TO ALL PEOPLE.

Everyone should be able to fill the plate with **nutritious, safe, sustainable and affordable food**. However, Europe's urban areas face challenges to ensure availability of healthy, sustainably produced food for all inhabitants and especially for people facing systemic barriers. Promising initiatives taken by municipalities to change the architecture of food choice often fail to become embedded in the wider policy context and to reach food-deprived and vulnerable groups.

FoodCLIC brings together actors from politics, science and civil society to support the development of **integrated urban food policies** - i.e. policies that facilitate the accessibility and availability of healthy and sustainably produced food for all people and in particular for vulnerable communities. Given the interconnectedness of food concerns with other (policy) sectors, FoodCLIC wants to ensure that **urban planning always incorporates food considerations**.

TAKING ACTION IN 8 CITY-REGIONS.

The EU-funded project supports the creation of sustainable urban food environments in eight city-regions, consisting of an urban centre and its surrounding rural (agriculturally used) area. These city-regions share the ambition of a **food system transformation** that is brought forward through the improvement of their **urban food environments** (and the interrelated urban food systems).

FoodCLIC wants to ensure that all inhabitants have access to **affordable, healthy and sustainably sourced food**.

AARHUS
Aarhus University
Aarhus Municipality

AMSTERDAM
City of Amsterdam
Food Connect Foundation
(Stichting Voedsel Verbindt)
VU Foundation (Stichting VU)

BARCELONA
Metropolitan Area of Barcelona
InstiCaixa ARIS Research Institute

BERLIN
Humboldt University of Berlin
Berlin Food Policy Council

BRNO
City of Brno
Transilvania University of Brno

BUDAPEST
Municipality of Budapest
ESSRG Nonprofit Kft

LISBON
Faculty of Medicine, University of Lisbon
Municipal Environmental Government Agency (EMG)

LUCCA
Municipality of Capannori
University of Pisa

SUPPORTING RESEARCH AND NETWORK PARTNERS:

Cardiff University, United Kingdom
CARIFLO Factory SRL, Italy
European Food Banks Federation, Belgium
CARIFLO Foundation, Italy
Foundation Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change (CMCC), Italy

ICLEI - Local Governments for Sustainability - Europe, Germany
ICLEI - Local Governments for Sustainability - Germany
ICLEI - Local Governments for Sustainability - Africa, South Africa
World Association of the Major Metropolises (Metropolis), France
University of Surrey, United Kingdom
Institute of Social Sciences, Portugal

LET'S TAKE A CLOSER LOOK.

URBAN FOOD ENVIRONMENTS

FOOD POLICY NETWORKS

THE CLIC: FOOD SYSTEM INTEGRATION

FOODCLIC. WE ARE CONNECTING PEOPLE, FOOD, POLICY & PLACES.

Funded by the European Union

CONTACT SITEMAP SEARCH LEGAL DATA PROTECTION

Figure 6: Screenshot of FoodCLIC website, About page.

2.3 BLOG

The **BLOG** is a space, where newsworthy project updates, information on upcoming events and “deep dives” into certain topical (or theoretical) areas (e.g. “urban food environments”) are published. Blog items will be regularly published to inform website visitors about the latest developments in the project, project results and recent publications that are available for download.

Figure 7: Screenshot of FoodCLIC website, BLOG page, which will be complemented by further items in the course of the project.

2.4 CONTACT

The contact page provides visitors with information on how to get in touch with the project partners (through the centrally managed email address foodclic.beta@vu.nl, managed by the project coordinator, VU Foundation). The project coordinator, VU Foundation, is taking care of emails and requests sent to the central email address and will ensure that each enquiry is dealt with as needed.

As soon as the project's is represented on social media, the links to its social media profile(s) will be published on the CONTACT page of the website.

Figure 8: Screenshot of FoodCLIC website, Contact page.

3. TECHNICAL FEATURES, WEBSITE MAINTENANCE AND DATA SAFETY

ICLEI Europe collaborated with an external agency to develop the FoodCLIC branding and web design, whereas ICLEI Europe itself took care of the **web development** (programming).

ICLEI Europe takes care of the **website maintenance** and hosts the website on its own servers in Germany. All data collection and maintenance are strictly GDPR aligned.

The **website content** is managed by using the web content management system “*Drupal*”. ICLEI Europe will use the system to keep the content of the website up-to-date and of high quality.

The **website design** is responsive, ensuring that the website is accessible and easy to navigate regardless of the device (desktop, mobile) used to access the website.

The website is accessible at the **URL** www.foodclic.eu. The URL has been purchased by ICLEI Europe for the first 3 project years (maximum possible period). The rights to the **domain** of the FoodCLIC website will be extended as soon as this possibility is given.

In the course of the project, the website is going to be filled with (more) content and relevant project updates, results and publications. For the duration of the project, ICLEI Europe is responsible for the website content management and website maintenance and will rely on input, regular updates and **content submissions** from all project partners to keep the website at high quality and to continuously offer added value to visitors.

The website will be kept online (unmaintained) for some years after the end of the project.

The project will also explore opportunities keep the Knowledge Hub and its contents online after the project has ended.

PARTNERS

CONTACT US:

www.foodclik.eu

foodclik.beta@vu.nl

#foodclik

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